

The Influence of Guidance Counselling on Business Education Programmes in Nigeria's Tertiary Institution

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Abstract

Guidance Counselling are essential in business education programmes; Business education deals with the empowerment necessary to meet business challenges in the business world or society. The study investigated the influence of Guidance Counselling on business education programmes in Nigeria Tertiary Institutions. The aim of the study was highlighted, and two research questions were formulated. The theoretical framework for this study is hinged on Decision Making Theory. A descriptive survey design was used to carry out the study. The target population for the study are counsellors, business education lecturers and students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used to select 230 respondents for this study. 1.7% of the samples are from the south-west- 23.9% from the south-south, 13.5% from the North-west, and 10.9% from the North-central. 37.4% of the respondents were male, and 62.6% were female. Percentile, mean, and standard deviations were used to analyse the data from the study. The result from the study indicates a general agreement among the respondents that Guidance Counselling can influence business education programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions. It was recommended, among others, that national awareness and orientation on the usefulness of Business Education in Nigeria should be increased. Counsellors must be encouraged through retraining or in-service courses, workshops and conferences regularly to give the students updated information about the world of work.

Key Words: Guidance Counselling, Business Education, Students and Nigeria Tertiary Institution,

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Introduction

Business education is a tool universally recognised for solutions to the world's socio-economic problems. Through business education, problems of poverty, unemployment and security would be curbed or minimised. The aim of business education, according to National Policy on Education (2012), is to provide a trained workforce in applied science, technology and commerce, particularly at sub-professional grades, provide technical knowledge and business skills required for agriculture, industries, commercial and economic development, give training and impact the needed skills leading to the production of artisans, technicians and other skilled personnel who will be enterprising and self-reliant, enable our young men and women to have intelligent understanding of the increasing complexity of technology, and give an introduction to professional studies in engineering and other technologies.

Despite the laudable importance of business education, it is observed that student's general behaviour towards the programme could be more impressive and encouraging. It is not a hidden fact that the need for introducing a business education programme is not felt as students have an unserious disposition towards the programme. In Nigeria, it is sad to mention that business education has remained a subordinate discipline in terms of societal recognition, interest and choice among tertiary students. It is dismal that Nigerian students believe that business education is reserved for students who cannot succeed in areas like science or social science. According to Azubuike (2011), students might not understand business education and, consequently, develop some contempt and aversion for the programme. Guidance Counselling can influence business education programmes by helping students understand and use their educational, vocational and personal opportunities wisely. They can develop as a form of systematic assistance whereby students achieve satisfactory adjustment to their study and life. The aim of Guidance Counselling is to promote the growth of the individual in self-direction and help to examine how to tap into existing resources or develop new ones that enhance their lives and relationship. This has urged the researchers to investigate the influence of Guidance Counselling on business education programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Specifically, the study examines;

1. The attitude of business education students in Nigeria tertiary institutions towards the programme.
2. The influence of Guidance Counselling on a business education programme in Nigeria tertiary institution.

Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions: -

1. What is the attitude of business education students in Nigerian tertiary institutions towards the programme?
2. How does Guidance Counselling influence business education programme in Nigerian tertiary institution?

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework for this study is hinged on Decision Making Theory by Tiedeman and O'Hara (1963). They focused on decision-making and recognised two phases: anticipating and adjusting to a choice (Sharf, 1997, p.370). They see the career decision-making process as a continuous process throughout life. Tiedeman and O'Hara divide the anticipation stage of decision-making into four stages that are only sometimes sequential or age-related.

Individuals can also be at different stages simultaneously for different career decisions. (Sharf, 1997, p.370 – 373):

Anticipation or Preoccupation Phase

1. Exploration – individuals may follow leads unsystematically, possibly imagining and fantasising or worrying about their deepest fears.
2. Crystallisation – typically represents the stabilisation of thought. Thoughts and ideas are more ordered, and up and downsides of choices may occur. Temporary choices may occur as well.
3. Choice – people may have varying confidence levels in their choice, and choices may vary in complexity. Sometimes there is conscious awareness of choice; sometimes, there may not be.
4. Clarification – time allows for reassessing the choice and clarifying it. If questioned, the individual may return to the exploration stage.

The previous stages lead to the implementation of and adjustment to a choice (Sharf, 1997, pp. 373 – 375). The implementation phase deals with carrying out the decision made in the previous phase:

Implementation of the accommodation phase

1. Induction – the individual implements their choice.
2. Reformation – the changes the individual needs to make to fit in with their new situation, following the choice and implementation.
3. Integration – the stage where the newness wears off, and the new situation feels familiar to the individual.

Like other change and decision-making theories, Tiedeman's theory can offer a good framework for guidance counsellors with students daily. It can be used as a model to help a student through any change and to help them recognise where they are and why they are feeling the way they do.

Concept of Guidance Counselling on Business Education Programme

It is expected that counselling should direct the affairs of those who seek it, many need to learn what counselling is, and failure to understand its true aim has led to mistakes. Guidance Counselling in schools encourage students to grow and realise their full potential. Business education occupies a strategic place in the history of education in Nigeria. It is vital to national development as it seeks to build and improve vocational knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for employment and advancement in business. Business education involves teaching skills and operations of the business industry; this field of education occurs at multiple levels: secondary school, undergraduate, post-graduate, Doctoral, and internships. An education in business varies significantly in its curriculum and popularity worldwide. Career development is an integral part of an education in business (Wikipedia, 2021). The main objective of business education is to help students learn about business by teaching them various business-related subjects and how to deal with finances, taxes and other business-related things. The earliest form of business education was apprenticeship training; at that time, an individual had to learn a trade under another person who had the skill for the trade or who was experienced in a particular area; after learning the trade, the length of time for training was based on how fast the apprentice could learn the skill. The individual may decide to start working with his master and be receiving a token sum or be freed. As time went on and businesses became large, people needed educational certificates to back it up; this gave business education a place in the formal setting. Business education deals with the

empowerment necessary to meet business challenges in a dynamic business world or society. It offers recipients the ability to cope with the emerging changes in education and business, where the person is expected to manifest all the skills acquired while in training (Sulaiman, 2018). Business education holds much promise for the recent privatisation of government parastatals and establishments, which seek to inject the principles and strategies of business management into these establishments for greater efficiency on profitable results. One major thing that stands out clearly about business education is that it is a programme that provides skills for the recipients to gain employment in the business community while, at the same time, such recipients are helpful to themselves. The pathway to this is not through a rote-learning process but a practical-oriented discipline. This is where Guidance Counselling come to help business education students be adequately informed about the expectations of their intentions.

Guidance Counselling as a profession are interested in helping individuals make good use of existing opportunities within their environment. Also, it helps individuals adapt to situations quickly without much difficulty. In the words of Akinade (2012), Guidance Counselling take the lead in helping people to make choices and decisions in life. Guidance Counselling play a role in students' career decisions. Olorungbemi (2013) sees Guidance Counselling as a specialised form of assisting people to be fully aware of themselves and become fulfilled. The definitions by these authors have made it clear that Guidance Counselling are the heartbeats of entrepreneurship since it involves individuals who need to be helped to realise their potential and capabilities in what they are capable of achieving within a given environment and with a little financial base. In Guidance and Counseling, a professional counsellor carries out many services, immensely benefiting entrepreneurs. They include; information service, educational service, vocational service, orientation service, appraisal service, counselling service, referral service, placement and follow-up services (Okobiah & Okorodudu, 2004; Egbochuku, 2008; Nwachuku, 2009; Adamu & Mora, 2010). These services exist in schools and non-school settings, and the essence is to reach out to people of different backgrounds with different aspirations in life to achieve their human endeavours.

The influence of Guidance Counselling would help individuals develop abilities, skills and understanding of the vocational opportunity available to them. The main focus of Guidance Counselling is to aid the individual in exploring and participating in his development towards self-reliant and fulfilment (Osuntuyi & Olowe, 2016); guidance and Counseling can help business education students in the following ways;

1. It will give the students an appropriate understanding of themselves and possible social, educational and occupational opportunities.
2. It helps students develop a scale of values to apply to their self-knowledge and knowledge of opportunities they have gained.
3. It helps students to consider realistically issues relating to lifestyle and work out the relationship between them.
4. It helps students appreciate the need for developmental planning for their future work and leisure.
5. It will foster students' realisation of self-knowledge and adequate understanding of available opportunities, allowing them to control their lives and futures.
6. It helps students to develop a sense of personal worth independently of their scholastic achievement. This can be done partly by helping them acquire personal competence in coping with various non-occupational challenges.

7. It assists the students in developing an awareness of the world of work and utilises the school and community resources to that end.
8. It assists the students in understanding their strengths, weaknesses, interest, values, potentialities and limitations.
9. It will help the students better understand the world of work by acquiring skills and attitudes in work-related programmes.
10. It will ensure that students understand the conditions and values they will find when they leave school.
11. It will allow the students to explore and assess different lifestyles and work styles, form an acceptable self-concept and adopt an acceptable lifestyle congruent with their chosen occupation.
12. It assists the business students to study and understand the full range of opportunities that will be open to them and to visualise probable future trends in such opportunities.
13. It will provide the students with suitable conditions to grow in self-understanding and develop the capacity for self-defectiveness and decision-making.

Methodology

A descriptive survey design was used to carry out the study. The target population for the study are counsellors, business education lecturers and students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used to select 160 business education students, 61 business education lecturers and 9 counsellors in four out of six geopolitical zones in Nigeria. Overall, a total of 230 participants – 86 males and 144 females constitute the sample size. The research instrument consists of sections A and B. Section A sought demographic data on age, gender, profession and zones.

In contrast, section B contained ten items that elicit information on the influence of Guidance Counselling on business education programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions. The instruments used for this study is a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire titled: that was designed to be ticked (✓) using Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD). A mean value score of 3.0 and above is accepted as 'agree' while lower than 3.0 is 'disagree'. The decision value is gotten by $[(1+2+3+4+5)/5]$.

The validity of the instrument was established through content validity. It was subjected to scrutiny by experts in measurement and evaluation. Based on their corrections and suggestions, the final version of the instrument was drawn. Reliability was tested using Cronbach Alpha, giving a value of 0.88. Copies of the instrument were administered virtually with the help of research assistants. Percentile, mean, and standard deviations were used to analyse the data from the study.

RESULT

Table 1: Demographic Data

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Profession		
Business Education Students	160	69.6
Business Education Lecturer	61	26.5
Counsellors	9	3.9
Total	230	100
Zone		

South-west	119	51.7
South-south	55	23.9
North-west	31	13.5
Northcentral	25	10.9
Total	230	100
Gender		
Male	86	37.4
Female	144	62.6
Total	230	100
Age		
19 - 29	160	69.6
35 - 45	27	11.7
46 - 55	17	7.4
56 - 65	26	11.3
Total	230	100

Two hundred and thirty respondents who are business education students – 160 (69.6%), business education lecturers 61 (26.5%) and institution counsellors 9 (3.9%) were sampled across south-west- 119 (51.7%), south-south – 55 (23.9%), North-west – 31 (13.5%), Northcentral- 25 (10.9%) in Nigeria. 86 (37.4%) of the respondents were male, and 144 (62.6%) were female. 160 (69.6%) of the respondents are between the age of 19 to 29 years, 27 (11.7%) of the respondents are between 35 to 45 years of age, 17 (7.4%) of the respondents are between 46 to 55 years of age, 26 (11.3%) between 56 to 65 years.

Research Question 1: What is the attitude of business education students in Nigerian tertiary institutions towards the programme?

The data collected were analysed to answer this research question, as shown in Table 2 below:

Attitude of Business Education Students in Nigeria's Tertiary Institutions towards the Programme

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of items in the table

Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
1. Most business education students decided to study the course in tertiary institution	4.07	0.93	Agreed
2. Business education students are likely to apply the knowledge learnt in the world of work	3.84	1.81	Agreed
3. Business education students are only studying to get a degree	3.12	1.23	Agreed

Table 2 above presents four items used to solicit information on the level of agreement or disagreement with various statements from the respondents. The mean score ranged between 3.12 and 4.07. The variation around the mean was checked by the coefficient of variation and revealed that the standard deviations are small and, therefore, a good representation of individual consensus.

Items 1 and 2 revealed a mean score of 4.07 (SD = 0.93) and 3.84 (SD = 1.81), respectively, which indicates a general agreement by the respondents that most business education students decided to study the course in tertiary institutions and are likely to apply the

knowledge learnt in the world of work. However, Item 3 showed a mean score of 3.12 (SD = 1.23), indicating that students only study to get a degree.

Research Question 2: How do Guidance Counselling influence business education programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions?

The data collected were analysed to answer this research question, as shown in Table 3 below:

Guidance and Counseling Influence Business Education Programme in Nigeria Tertiary Institution

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of items in the table

ITEM STATEMENTS	Mean	SD	Remark
4. Business Education students often visit the school counselling unit	3.05	1.07	Agreed
5. Guidance & counselling can help improve students' Academic Performance and help them understand their career path clearly	4.27	0.86	Agreed
6. I believe Guidance Counselling can make business education programmes more appealing and impactful to students in the tertiary institution	4.07	1.12	Agreed
7. Guidance Counselling can improve students' understanding of business education	4.27	0.47	Agreed
8. Guidance Counselling can help business education students realise their potential and what they can achieve in the business education programme	4.16	0.44	Agreed
9. The Business Education Department should work with the institution's Guidance Counselling Unit to provide career assessment and guidance to applicants at the interview phase of the admission process	4.26	0.70	Agreed
10. Students need to check in with school counsellors often, even when they feel they do not need extra support	3.97	0.74	Agreed

Table 3 above presents seven items used to solicit information on the level of agreement or disagreement with various statements from the respondents. The mean score ranged between 3.05 and 4.27. The variation around the mean was checked by the coefficient of variation and revealed that the standard deviations are small and, therefore, a good representation of individual consensus.

Items 4 to 10 with mean scores of 3.05 (SD =1.07); 4.27 (SD = 0.86); 4.07 (SD =1.12); 4.27 (SD =0.47); 4.16 (SD = 0.44); 4.26 (SD = 0.70) and 3.97 (SD = 0.74) respectively indicate general agreement by the respondents that Guidance Counselling can influence business education programme in Nigeria tertiary institution.

Summary of Findings

1. Two hundred and thirty respondents were sampled for this study. 1.7% of the samples are from the south-west- 23.9% from the south-south, 13.5% from the North-west, and 10.9% from the North-central. 37.4% of the respondents were male, and 62.6% were female.
2. The result from the study indicates a general agreement among the respondents that most business education students decided to study the course in tertiary institutions and are likely to apply the knowledge learnt in the world of work. However, the result also indicates that students only study for a degree.

3. The result from the study also indicates general agreement among the respondents that Guidance Counselling can influence business education programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

Business Education is concerned with developing the skills and knowledge needed to function well as an officer, self-employed or self-reliant individual. The study has shown that most business education student has a positive attitude towards the business education programme in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Most of the students decided to study the course in tertiary institutions and are likely to apply the knowledge learnt in the world of work. The study has also revealed that Guidance Counselling can influence business education programmes in Nigerian tertiary institutions. Students need to be encouraged or properly guided on their career development; with the help of the counsellor, they will help the business education students to stay put in their career and to continue.

Recommendation

Based on the findings from this research, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. There should be national awareness and orientation on the usefulness of Business Education in Nigeria.
2. Counsellors must be encouraged through retraining or in-service courses, workshops and conferences regularly to give the students updated information about the world of work.
3. Tertiary Institutions should implement a career development programme for business education students that expose them to a typical workplace and knowledge about career and develop sensible attitudes to the problems involved in choosing employment. Such a programme should be managed and coordinated by the counsellor.

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